

EARTH SCIENCES

PROBLEMS OF SOLID MINERALS EXPLORATION AND DEVELOPMENT IN THE WORLD OCEAN

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Abstract

The article considers the constraints that prevent the extraction of metallic minerals from the World Ocean floor. Namely, the lack of mining experience, technical and technological complexes, environmental and economic constraints are becoming a particularly serious obstacle. Geological study, exploration and extraction of metallic minerals of the World Ocean floor form a major intersectoral issue of the most significant national importance. The solution of this complex problem will determine Russia's place in the world market of mineral raw materials, the possibility of meeting the domestic needs of growing economic power and export potential beyond the first half of the XXI century.

Keywords: the World Ocean, ferromanganese nodules, cobalt-manganese crusts, deep-sea polymetallic sulfides, mining operations, contracts with the International Seabed Authority (ISA), environmental and economic constraints, mineral raw materials, minerals, geological study, exploration.

The problems of studying and developing the mineral resource potential of the World Ocean are based on the specificity and uniqueness of ore accumulations. There are no direct analogues of ferromanganese nodules (FMN), cobalt-manganese crusts (CMC) and deep-sea polymetallic sulfides (DPS) among onshore deposits and ore occurrences. The scientific and methodological foundations of ocean geological exploration, the requirements for their staging, categorization of reserves, evaluation of the density representativeness of the exploration network, sampling volumes and other parameters have been developed only on the basis of conditional analogies with land objects. There are no internationally accepted standards on this point.

Meanwhile, the ore bodies of the ocean floor are fundamentally different from those on the mainland. The obvious differences are:

1. the absence of the enclosing rock environment and the continuous "outcrop" of ore accumulations;
2. nearly all FMN accumulations and their occurrence on an unbound base of oceanic sediments are of the placer;

3. the heterogeneous nature of the contacts between the CMC and the underlying bedrock;

4. the absence of useful mineral components (Ni, Cu, Co) in FMN and CMC, which excludes the isolation of differentiated concentrates of the relevant metals using conventional primary ore processing (enrichment) technologies;

5. insufficient information on the internal mineralogical, geochemical and structural zoning of individual DPS accumulations, and as a consequence, the uncertainty about the formation affiliation of DPS, and accordingly about their geological and industrial classification which is the scientific basis for the methodology of exploration, evaluation and calculation of reserves. [1]

Meanwhile, the polyformation nature of DPS is observed at the global level. In particular, their accumulations in the Atlantic Ocean and the western part of the Indian Ocean are characterized by the predominance of copper over zinc, while in the Pacific Ocean and the eastern part of the Indian Ocean the ratio is the opposite. It is possible that each DPS accumulation will

be characterized by individual mineral and geochemical specificity. Without knowledge of these regularities, the results of estimates of the resource potential of DPS may have fundamental errors. In connection with these features, only the volumes of DPS ore mass can be estimated with a certain reliability leaving its qualitative and quantitative composition of metals at an indefinite level.

The marine environment has its own specifics. It is one thing to look for new deposits in the vicinity of the known ones or “ore from ore”, and quite another is to find a deposit on the seabed. The problem is that the seabed in many places is covered with a layer of silt that reaches tens or even hundreds of meters. Thus, if something is now planned to be mined in the World Ocean, this substance should be on the surface of the seabed.

The lack of experience in mining metallic minerals on the World Ocean floor also predetermines the lack of a technical and technological complex for the implementation of this rather complicated production cycle. So far, no country or business structure in the world has declared its readiness for large-scale work to create technical and technological complexes for the oceanic mining of solid minerals. Existing vessels can only conduct geological exploration with the selection of low-volume samples from the ore mass. There are no stationary operating mining complexes adapted for the delivery of large ore masses from the ocean floor and their release from natural humidity and transportation over long distances, which also ensure safety in emergency situations. However, the development of mining equipment has begun in the PRC, Japan, the Republic of Korea, India, France, and Germany.

There are also environmental constraints, which become a particularly serious obstacle if the site is located at a shallow depth. As a rule, in such cases the seabed is densely populated, and mining will have a detrimental effect on marine biota. Obviously, this component contributes to the cost of the work. No single solution has been developed here yet.

For example, in the case of nodules, a “chessboard method” is proposed where the seabed is divided into cells, and minerals are extracted from the “black cells”, while marine organisms can move to the “white cells”. Nevertheless, a ready-made technological solution on how to extract minerals with minimal environmental damage has not yet been developed.[2]

The existing regulatory framework needs to be improved to avoid long-term damage to the marine environment based on high quality environmental impact assessments and mitigation strategies.

All this, in turn, should be based on comprehensive baseline studies to improve the understanding of deep-sea areas that are not yet been sufficiently explored or not studied at all.

According to the experts of the International Union of Conservation Experts (IUCN), the “Code on

Subsoil and Subsoil Use” does not have sufficient information about deep-water areas. ““We are operating in the dark,” says Carl Gustaf Lundin, Director of IUCN’s Global Marine and Polar Programme. “Our current understanding of the deep sea does not allow us to effectively protect marine life from mining operations. And yet, exploration contracts are being granted even for those areas that host highly unique species. Exploitation of minerals using current technologies could potentially destroy the rich deep-sea life forever, benefiting only a few, and disregarding future generations.””[3]

So far, there is little empirical data on the impacts on the ecosystem during deep-sea mining, but the potential consequences are of concern.

In the opinion of scientists, direct physical damage to marine habitats is one of them, i.e. plowing the ocean floor with the help of machinery (like deforestation) leads to mixing of the primary soil with the rest of the seabed sediments. These actions will make the water turbid and may lead to suffocation of the inhabitants. Additional negative impact is exerted by:

- toxic pollution from leaks and spills;
- noise and vibration, as well as littering of the water area from mining equipment and surface vessels.[4]

All precautions to protect the marine environment must become a core part of any mining regulations, which currently do not really exist.

The absence of technical and technological complexes creates uncertainty in solving environmental problems, training engineering, technical and working personnel for the field of offshore mining. The link between technical and technological, environmental and human resources is obvious. However, without solving primary problems of this sequence, it is impossible to determine the subsequent ones.

The mining of FMN and CMC has another technical and technological problem. The impossibility of obtaining metal-separate concentrates from them indicates the need to create a technology for separating metals by ore types. The problem of the specifics of the primary processing of ores does not apply to DPS, since their mineral composition, structural and textural features are quite close to traditional ores of polymetallic land deposits. That allows using existing technologies (possibly their partial modernization) to obtain metal concentrates.

The economic aspects of developing Russian ore region are contradictory. First, it is clear that the already identified resource potential of FMN, CMC, and DPS is significant (Table 1). As the reserves and resources of the land are developed, the transition to oceanic ores will become inevitable. This process will be of a global scale.

Table 1

Total resource potential of Russia's exploration areas

№ item	Types of ores	Mn, mln tonnes	Ni, mln tonnes	Cu, mln tonnes	Co, mln tonnes	Zn, mln tonnes	Au, mln tonnes	Ag, mln tonnes
1	FMN	120,4	5,66	4,5	0,99	-	-	-
2	CMC	33,3	0,75	-	0,85	-	-	-
3	DPS	-	-	4,6	-	0,88	160,5	2491
4	Total	153,7	6,41	9,1	1,84	0,88	160,5	2491
5	Share of Russia's land potential	32,6	27,0	8,8	283,1	1,3	0,85	1,8

Secondly, the timing of the active development of the World Ocean resources is impossible to specify clearly. However, it can be predicted that this process will begin in the second half of this century. Is this relatively distant time horizon that is tempting for business to invest in future success? It is unlikely that a positive answer to this question will be received in the near future. However, the lost time for advanced geological exploration, receiving rights for mining and the creation of a technical and technological complex will result in major losses in the future.

Considering the economic problems of technical and technological support, some favorable factors should be taken into account. In particular, it is obvious that the extraction of FMN, CMC and partly DPS will not be accompanied by stripping operations since ore accumulations are brought to the surface of the ocean floor. The mining of FMN and CMC will not be associated with excavating, drilling and blasting. These factors will not only reduce the cost of mining, but also mitigate environmental problems by the virtual absence of waste to be disposed of. The need for drilling wells and carrying out blasting operations is not excluded in the case of DPS. However, this issue requires further study.

The high contents of the main and by-product components and the large volume of ore mass indicate in favor of the development of FMN, CMC and DPS. Manganese and cobalt contained in the composition of FMN and CMC are of undoubted interest for the raw material supply of Russia in the current and mid-term periods. The fact that FMN have unique sorption properties also cannot be ignored. These properties might become indispensable in solving ecological problems in the treatment of harmful liquid and gaseous wastes from metallurgical and other industries.

However, the high natural value of oceanic ores determined by analogy with traditional deposits is not a representative economic criterion to prove their competitiveness even with high ore quality and favorable conditions for their extraction. Such evidence can only be the ratio between the costs of mining (including transportation and primary ore processing) and the natural value of ores. Meanwhile, the costs cannot be determined without knowledge of the methods, techniques and technology of the entire complex of ore extraction and processing. [5]

The weighty geopolitical aspect of presence in the World Ocean has always appeared in international relations. This is evidenced by indisputable historical facts. In particular, in the early period of great geo-

graphical discoveries, the colonization of the discovered territories did not give rise to major confrontations between states. The strong arguments determining the affiliation of these territories were demonstrated by the pickets carrying the flags of the pioneer countries. However, exactly the problems of territorial ownership soon enough became the main factors in the emergence of political confrontations and even military conflicts.

Currently, the world is at the initial stage of identifying and exploring solid minerals of the oceans. The number of contracts with ISA has not even exceeded the third dozen. But it is clear that the number of discoveries will increase over time, and the "queue" for contracts will grow proportionally, which will certainly become a cause for the emergence of more than just opportunistic contradictions.

This process has not yet escalated for a number of reasons. Firstly, no country has yet started mining operations to obtain a material product with a satisfactory economic effect. The first results in this direction with the inclusion of oceanic metal mining in the framework of the commercial sphere will change the situation dramatically, and the competition dictated by large industrial and financial corporations will become inevitable. Secondly, global material production does not yet experience a shortage of sources for the production of metals and alloys. Their deficit in different countries is compensated through various forms of foreign economic relations. But against this market background, there is already a clear tendency to monopolize the supply of ores of some major types of minerals.

The steeply increasing vector of the mineral use in human history cannot be ignored. Only in the second half of the XX century, 80–85% of the total volume of iron ores mined by mankind in its entire documented history was used. During this period, the consumption of non-ferrous and rare metal constituents of FMN, CMC and DPS increased by 3-5 times compared to the same period in the past. This process will intensify in the XXI century due to the inevitable increase in the range and absolute quantity of manufactured goods, the rapid growth of production in the electronics industry, communications equipment, the increasing pace of space exploration, and the creation of new defense facilities.

The geological study, exploration and extraction of metallic minerals from the World Ocean floor form a major intersectoral problem of crucial national importance. The solution of this complex problem will determine Russia's place in the world market of mineral raw materials, the possibility of meeting the domestic needs of growing economic power and export potential

beyond the first half of the XXI century. Equally important is the geopolitical factor of securing Russia's rights to geological exploration and mining operations in the World Ocean. The solution of this complex problem can be achieved through the implementation of active actions in a number of areas.

The first priority is to create conditions for the indisputable acquisition of a contractual right to mine FMN in the Clarion-Clipperton exploration zone. The International Seabed Authority (ISA) will start accepting applications in July 2023 from companies that want to develop the ocean floor. [6] Currently, only geological exploration is allowed in the Clarion-Clipperton zone, and full-scale mining has not yet begun. However, the situation may soon change: the tiny Pacific island nation of Nauru has introduced a "two-year rule", which obliges ISA to develop and implement rules governing the deep-sea mining industry within two years. [7]

However, it is important that mining projects are sustainable, and this is not yet clear for deep sea mining. The fact is that the Clarion-Clipperton zone is the habitat of xenophyophores which are unicellular organisms that live in the deepest ocean trenches under extreme pressure, low oxygen and no sunlight. Xenophyophores are an essential component of ocean ecosystems: they process silt, thereby providing a habitat for crustaceans, molluscs and other inhabitants of the seabed. In the Clarion-Clipperton zone 34 species of xenophyophores previously unknown to science have already been discovered. Xenophyophores are very sensitive to environmental changes due to human activity, thus deep-sea mining can be dangerous for them and for the entire ecosystem of which they are an important part. Eco-activists believe that the new industry can cause irreversible damage to the ocean ecosystem about which we still know little.

According to geological and natural conditions of localization, accumulations of FMN, CMC and DPS do not fit into the existing industrial and genetic classification of ore deposits and the classification of deposits based on the complexity of the structure created on this basis. This leads to ambiguity in the level of knowledge, insufficient specificity in the categorization of reserves and resources. Russia could take the lead in the development of an international classification for oceanic ores. There are favorable conditions for such a promising initiative. They are determined by the fact that Russia is one of the leaders in the study of geology in the World Ocean. In addition to the practical results obtained, Russian marine geologists possess fundamental, universally recognized general geological and mineralogical reports on the structure and ore content of the ocean floor.

The possibility of implementing mining operations of FMN in the coming years (and in 15–20 years of CMC and DPS) dictates the need for detailed market research on the current state, short-term, mid-term and long-term development of global and domestic metal markets. These studies should be closely connected to the program documents and options for long-term forecasts for economic and social development, territorial

and field placement of new industries and demographic transformations.

The above-mentioned problems of studying and developing solid minerals of the World Ocean are far from complete. They indicate the need to create an effective management system for studying and developing solid minerals of Russian exploration areas in the World Ocean. The intersectoral significance of the problems and their multifaceted nature are obvious. In this regard, there is a need to determine a single coordinator for the activities of all participants.

The niche of scientific and applied developments, the creation of equipment and technology for an integrated system for the study and development of ocean solid minerals in the world market has not yet been occupied. The exceptional importance of filling this niche with Russia must be recognized and implemented.

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